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The family environment in the psychological development of 3- and 4-year-old children

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ABSTRACT: The fundamental purpose of this research is to disseminate the most relevant results of the study conducted with 3 and 4-year-old children at the Ramón Burneo Basic Education School in the Zalapa Bajo neighborhood. In the development of this research, scientific, analytical-synthetic, hermeneutic, and statistical methods were utilized; likewise, the direct observation technique was employed, and the Metric Scale of Intelligence Test was used as the instrument. The main result obtained indicates a noticeable advance in the students' performance, reaching 82% with a diagnostic equivalent of "Very Good," while 11% of the population obtained a "Good" diagnosis, and 7% of the population obtained a "Low" diagnosis. It is concluded that within the family environment, there is a lack of communication and attention toward the child, preventing them from developing adequately in the classroom. It is recommended to provide love, affection, and trust to the child to improve their psychic development.

KEYWORDS: The family environment, psychic development, initial education II.

1. INTRODUCTION

The family environment is considered a basic institution and constitutes an eminently existential setting, where a large number of experiences usually occur that induce intimate and essential life lessons derived from daily coexistence with the family. Within the home are parents, children, grandparents, aunts/uncles, etc., who form part of the family nucleus.

The family constitutes an entity where social interest and personal interest are present and intimately intertwined, given that, as the elementary cell of society, it contributes to its development and fulfills important functions in the formation of new generations (Martínez Gómez, 2003).

The family constitutes an entity where social interest and personal interest are present and intimately intertwined since, as the elementary cell of society, it contributes to its development and fulfills important functions in the formation of new generations; and, as a center of common-life relations between woman and man, between them and their children, and among everyone with their relatives, they satisfy affective and social human interests of the individual.

Child psychology not only aims to discover all the circumstances that influence psychic development, but also how they influence it; one of the main tasks of this science is to highlight the meaning of general conditions, thanks to which the child becomes a person.

These conditions are the properties of the child's organism (first and foremost, the structure and functioning of the brain) and the human society in which the child is raised. Human psychic life does not emerge if human conditions of life do not exist; to be human requires a brain, specific living conditions, and a certain education. However, each of these aspects has a different value.

The child inherits the structure and functioning of the organism. From birth, they possess a human nervous system, a brain capable of becoming the organ of psychic activity.

It is necessary to study the human being from their beginnings because, under the perspective and commentary of various experts on the subject, it is reflected that all social human conduct has its beginnings in the childhood of individuals.

Likewise, child development psychology is a branch of general psychology, which is responsible for studying changes in child behavior and the development of the abilities that little ones acquire.

It is worth mentioning the relevance of psychic development, which is characterized by various psychological functions such as intelligence, memory, and attention because they are vital in the development of the child.

Developmental psychology or evolutionary psychology studies the development of the child. It consists of the study of the way children change over time and how they remain themselves, from conception to adolescence. Depending on how the child evolves, it is important to study the changes and behaviors they present in order to achieve proper development and relationship skills within them (López Cardozo, 2010).

The child is an active subject of their own development, promoting it through their own personal characteristics of temperament, personality, and activity present in their life.

2. OBJECTIVE

To disseminate the most relevant results obtained from the development of the research project titled: *The family environment in the psychic development of children of 3 and 4 years of age at the Ramón Burneo Basic Education School in the Zalapa Bajo Neighborhood, El Valle Parish, Loja Canton. Period 2024-2025.*

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Family Environment

Children living in an environment that stimulates intelligence show better verbal, mathematical, and reasoning skills. And this environment is not confined to the school setting: studies point out that the higher the educational and occupational level of the parents, the higher the performance of their children.

Parents play a fundamental role in creating an intellectually stimulating environment for their offspring. The cognitive development of children and adolescents does not depend solely on the school environment. One of the most important factors is the educational and occupational level of both parents (Rodríguez, 2015).

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Family values are the principles that guide the way people behave within personal relationships held within the affinity of feelings, affection, and interests based on the mutual respect that individuals may have.

The family is the community where, during a person's life stage from birth to puberty, values and the proper use of utility are taught, where personal relationships and family stability are the foundations of freedom, security, and union within society; that is why the family initiates social life. The first things taught in the family are family values, which will be the basic elements for life in society and throughout the life of each individual.

The family relationship is the fundamental basis for living in a community and thus relating to other people, allowing the regulation of behavior for the collective well-being and to have a harmonious coexistence within society and in life (García, 2015).

Although the family, like any social institution, is a reality in transformation, it is at the same time capable of maintaining its own identity throughout the changes it experiences as a result of sociocultural transformations.

Its permanence is grounded in its origin, that is, in human nature, which does not change no matter how much social circumstances change. Likewise, it is worth noting that its origin leads it to be a universal fact, that is, a reality present in all cultures of all times (Fernández Córdoba, 2001).

Thus, the family continues to represent one of the spaces of coexistence and interaction with the greatest relevance for the development of human beings.

Psychic Development

The psychic development of the child depends on various conditions. Child psychology not only aims to discover all the circumstances that influence psychic development, but also how they influence it; one of the main tasks of this science is to highlight the meaning of general conditions, thanks to which the child becomes a person.

These conditions are the properties of the child's organism (first and foremost, the structure and functioning of the brain) and the human society in which the child is raised. Human psychic life does not emerge if human conditions of life do not exist; to be human requires a brain, specific living conditions, and a certain education (Shaffer, 2014).

The child is an active subject of their own development, promoting it through their own personal characteristics of temperament, personality, and activity present in their life.

Child development psychology is a branch of general psychology, which is responsible for studying changes in child behavior and the development of the abilities that little ones acquire. It consists of the study of the way children change over time and how they remain themselves, from conception to adolescence (López Cardozo, 2010).

Explanation refers to the causes of behavior. Prediction attempts to make a forecast about subsequent development, and modification consists of intervening to achieve optimal development in children.

It is essential to point out that the education a child receives during the first years of life is decisive for their psychic development and their future life, as they will develop as a human being. The environmental richness surrounding the child and the help of adults in the child learning process are important in the development of their psyche (Delval, 2008).

At this age, adult help should not be directive, but rather in the form of collaboration. Let us highlight that in the third year of life, the actions the child performs with objects develop psychic processes. Toys like plastic cubes and balls can develop different aspects of psychomotor skills

Initial Education II

Initial Education is the process of accompanying the comprehensive development of boys and girls under 5 years of age, and its objective is to enhance their learning and promote their well-being through meaningful and timely experiences provided in stimulating, healthy, and safe environments.

Boys and girls of this age naturally seek to explore, experiment, play, and create—activities they carry out through interaction with others, with nature, and with their culture. Parents, family members, and other people in their environment are very important and must provide them with care, protection, and affection to ensure the formation of happy and healthy children, capable of learning and developing (Aguaded, M. 2000).

The Initial Education curriculum in force since 2014 centers on the recognition that child development is comprehensive and encompasses all the aspects that comprise it (cognitive, social, psychomotor, physical, and affective), which are interrelated with one another and occur in the natural and cultural environment. To guarantee this comprehensive approach, it is necessary to promote learning opportunities, stimulating exploration in rich and diverse environments, with warmth, affection, and positive interactions.

4. SUMMARY OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Point to nose, eyes, mouth.

Table 1

Indicators	f	%
Performs it	4	100
Does not perform it	--	--
Total	4	100

Source: Metric Scale of Intelligence Test applied to the girls and boys of the Ramón Burneo Basic Education School.

Graph 1

Analysis and Interpretation

For Ortiz (2002), "Body Expression is the set of techniques that utilize the body and movement. It is the art that releases energies through movement and expression (Blanco Vega, 2009). According to the preceding table and graph, it was verified that 4 children, representing 100% of the population, performed the activity of pointing to the nose, eyes, and mouth without any difficulty, showing that when the children executed the activity, they felt confident and secure in themselves.

Children can satisfactorily distinguish the different sensory organs of their body; likewise, this allows the child to foster self-awareness to know themselves better and feel secure, achieving autonomous knowledge about their own humanity.

2. State their sex

Table 2

Indicators	f	%
Performs it	4	100
Does not perform it	--	--
Total	4	100

Source: Metric Scale of Intelligence Test applied to the girls and boys of the Ramón Burneo Basic Education School.

Graph 2

Analysis and Interpretation

Howard Gardner addresses self-knowledge and the ability to adapt one's own ways of acting based on that knowledge. This intelligence includes having an accurate image of oneself (one's own strengths and limitations), having awareness of inner moods, intentions, motivations, temperaments, and desires, and the capacity for self-discipline, self-understanding, and self-esteem (González Hueso, 2011).

According to the data obtained, it was verified that 4 children, representing 100% of the population, successfully answered the question stating their sex, as the girls and boys felt secure in themselves and confident when answering what they were asked.

Children's curiosity can manifest by looking at and touching themselves to explore their own bodies. They know how to distinguish their sex, thereby achieving the capacity to understand their physical characteristics; likewise, this also allows the child to develop comprehensively and understand the variable behaviors of each sex.

Discussion

Comparative table of the pre-test and post-test applied to girls and boys of 3 and 4 years of age at the Ramón Burneo Basic Education School.

PRE-TEST			POST-TEST		
1. Point to nose, eyes, mouth					
Indicator	f	%	Indicator	f	%
Performs it	4	100	Performs it	4	100
Does not perform it	--	--	Does not perform it	--	--
TOTAL	4	100	TOTAL	4	100
2. State their sex					
Indicator	f	%	Indicator	f	%
Performs it	4	100	Performs it	4	100
Does not perform it	--	--	Does not perform it	--	--
TOTAL	4	100	TOTAL	4	100

With the realization of the final result, according to the first table, it was evident that 4 children, representing 100% of the population, performed the activity of pointing to the nose, eyes, and mouth without any difficulty, demonstrating that children know how to differentiate their body's sensory organs, feeling secure in themselves when responding. On the other hand, the second table proved that 4 children, representing 100% of the population, successfully answered the question stating their sex; likewise, this allows the child to develop comprehensively and become familiar with the variable behaviors of each sex.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that the different activities carried out were well interpreted by the children, thus revealing that they correctly answer the questions presented, as they have the ability to discriminate the evaluated concepts such as: differentiating their sex and respectively their body's sensory organs, concluding with a positive development of the study conducted.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The right to education and information for children must be fostered by parents and teachers, as this will allow for a subsequent norm of coexistence within the home and in relation to the outside world. Likewise, efforts must be made to make their own identity known since the child expresses and feels through their body; therefore, it is important for them to know it, explore it, and experience it—not only its external and visible parts, but also those that they do not see but feel, which generate great interest and a big imagination in them.

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